

4-Quinazolones, Part VIII.

Synthesis of some Thiazolido (3,2-a) quinazolin-1,5(4H)-diones

S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury

The synthesis of 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy-, 7,8-dimethoxy- and 8-allyloxy-7-methoxy-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-diones is described.

We have shown earlier¹ that when 3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (V) was treated with an alkaline solution of sodium borohydride at room temperature for several hours and subsequently acidified 4-phenylthiazolido (3,2-a) quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (X) was formed by reduction of the 1,2-imine double bond (:C=N) followed by cyclodehydration. This facile reductive cyclisation reaction has now been extended to the preparation of three other thiazolido(3,2-a)-quinazolin-1,5(4H)-diones : XI, XII, XIII, which have substituents in the benzene ring.

Interaction of 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-,² 3,4-dimethoxy-³ and 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid⁴ with phenyl isothiocyanate furnished respectively 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy- (I), 6,7-dimethoxy- (II) and 7-allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) in good yields. By the action of excess ethereal diazomethane I was converted into II and both I and II, on treatment with methyl iodide in the presence of alkali, were transformed into 6,7-dimethoxy-2-mercaptomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IV). Thus

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| I : R = 6-OH-7-OCH ₃ ; R ₁ = H | X : R = H |
| II : R = 6,7-di-OCH ₃ ; R ₁ = H | XI : R = 7-OH-8-OCH ₃ |
| III : R = 6-OCH ₃ -7-Oallyl; R ₁ = H | XII : R = 7,8-di-OCH ₃ |
| IV : R = 6,7-di-OCH ₃ ; R ₁ = CH ₃ | XIII : R = 7-OCH ₃ -8-Oallyl |
| V : R = H; R ₁ = CH ₂ COOH | |
| VI : R = 6-OH-7-OCH ₃ ; R ₁ = CH ₂ COOH | |
| VII : R = 6,7-di-OCH ₃ ; R ₁ = CH ₂ COOH | |
| VIII : R = 6,7-di-OCH ₃ ; R ₁ = CH ₂ COOCH ₃ | |
| IX : R = 6-OCH ₃ -7-Oallyl; R ₁ = CH ₂ COOH | |

1. Part V. B. D. Singh and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 47.
2. Part VI. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Communicated.
3. Part VII. S. K. P. Sinha, P. K. Banerjee and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, Preceding paper.
4. Part III. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 46, 31.

while methyl iodide-alkali methylated both the phenolic hydroxyl and thiol groups, diazomethane selectively methylated only the phenolic OH. Condensation of the mercaptoquinazolones I, II and III with an alkaline solution of monochloroacetic acid yielded respectively 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy- (VI), 6,7-dimethoxy- (VII) and 7-allyloxy-6-methoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (IX). Both VI and VII when treated with diazomethane gave the same compound, methyl 6,7-dimethoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetate (VIII). Reduction of the alkaline solution of the acids : VI, VII and IX with excess sodium borohydride followed by acid-catalysed dehydration furnished respectively 7-hydroxy-8-methoxy- (XI), 7,8-dimethoxy- (XII) and 8-allyloxy-7-methoxy-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (XIII). Treatment with diazomethane converted XI into XII.

EXPERIMENTAL*

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (I) : A mixture of 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid² (2.95 g.; 0.01 mole) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.1 ml.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml.) was heated on a steam bath when immediately a clear solution was obtained. After 10 min., a solid separated out and the heating was continued for a total period of 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled, the solid filtered off, washed with a little ethanol and crystallised from acetic acid to give I as colorless plates (2.1 g.; 70%), m.p. 145-146°. (Found : C, 59.7; H, 4.2; N, 9.1. C₁₅H₁₂O₃N₂S requires C, 60.0; H, 4.0; N, 9.3%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (II) : (i) It was prepared as above from 3,4-dimethoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid³ (1.97 g.; 0.01 mole), phenyl isothiocyanate (1.1 ml.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml.) and the product was crystallised from acetic acid to afford II as colorless needles (2.85 g.; 91%), m.p. 297-298°. (Found : C, 61.2; H, 4.6; N, 9.0. C₁₆H₁₄O₃N₂S requires C, 61.0; H, 4.3; N, 8.9%).

(ii) I (0.75 g.) suspended in ether (10 ml.) was treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 1.2 g. of N-nitrosomethyl urea) and left overnight. The solid left after evaporating the ether was crystallised from acetic acid to yield II as colorless needles (0.6 g.; 75%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 297-298°.

7-Allyloxy-6-methoxy-2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (III) : Following the procedure described for the preparation of I, 4-allyloxy-3-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid⁴ (2.23 g.; 0.01 mole) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.1 ml.; 0.01 mole) in ethanol (20 ml.) yielded III which was crystallised from acetic acid to afford colorless needles (2 g.; 90%), m.p. 245-246°. (Found : C, 63.2; H, 5.0; N, 8.4. C₁₈H₁₆O₃N₂S requires C, 63.5; H, 4.7; N, 8.2%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-2-mercaptomethyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)one (IV) : (i) A solution of II (3.14 g.; 0.01 mole) in 5% alcoholic NaOH solution (20 ml.) was treated with CH₃I (0.65 ml.; 0.01 mole) with stirring and allowed to stand for 2 hr. at room temperature when colorless crystalline material separated out. It was collected, washed thoroughly with water and crystallised from dilute ethanol to furnish IV as colorless prisms (2.75 g.; 95%), m.p. 229-230°. (Found : C, 62.4; H, 5.0; N, 8.3. C₁₇H₁₆O₃N₂S requires C, 62.1; H, 4.8; N, 8.5%).

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected.

(ii) **1** (3 g.; 0.01 mole) dissolved in 5% alcoholic NaOH solution (20 ml.) was treated with CH_3I (1.3 ml.; 0.02 mole), stirred for 0.5 hr. and left for 2 hr. at room temperature. On dilution with water the precipitate that separated out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to give **IV** as colorless prisms (2.3 g.; 70%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 229-230°.

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (**VI**): To a solution of **I** (3 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml.), monochloroacetic acid (0.95 g.; 0.01 mole) was added and left overnight. It was acidified with conc. HCl, the precipitate that separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield **VI** as colorless needles (1.45 g.; 40%), m.p. 148-149°. (Found: C, 57.2; H, 4.1; N, 7.5. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 57.0; H, 3.9; N, 7.8%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (**VII**): It was prepared as the preceding compound by treating a solution of **II** (3.14 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml.) with monochloroacetic acid (0.95 g.; 0.01 mole). The product on crystallisation from ethanol gave **VII** as colorless needles (2.2 g.; 60%), m.p. 205-206°. (Found: C, 58.3; H, 4.6; N, 7.8. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 58.0; H, 4.3; N, 7.5%).

Methyl 6,7-dimethoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetate (**VIII**): (i) A suspension of **VII** (0.744 g.; 0.002 mole) in ether (10 ml.) was treated with ethereal diazomethane (from 1 g., of N-nitrosomethyl urea), kept overnight and worked up in the usual way. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished **VIII** as colorless needles (0.7 g.; 90%), m.p. 157-158°. (Found: C, 56.2; H, 4.8; N, 7.1. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 56.4; H, 4.6; N, 7.2%).

(ii) A slurry of **VI** (0.36 g.; 0.001 mole) in ether (10 ml.) was treated with ethereal diazomethane (from 1 g. N-nitrosomethyl urea), kept overnight and worked up in the usual way. The product was crystallised from ethanol to yield colorless needles (0.35 g.; 90%), m.p. 157-158°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained as in (i).

7-Allyloxy-6-methoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (**IX**): A solution of **III** (3.4 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml.) was treated with monochloroacetic acid (0.95 g.; 0.01 mole) and worked up as described for the preparation of **VI**. Crystallisation from ethanol afforded **IX** as colorless flakes (2.4 g.; 60%), m.p. 189-190°. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 4.7; N, 7.3. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 60.3; H, 4.5; N, 7.0%).

7-Hydroxy-8-methoxy-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (**XI**): To a solution of **VI** (3.58 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml.), NaBH_4 (1.54 g.; 0.04 mole) was added and left overnight. It was cooled, acidified with dil. HCl and the solid that separated out was filtered, washed successively with water, aq. NaHCO_3 and water. Crystallisation from ethanol gave the cyclised product **XI** as colorless irregular prisms (1.7 g.; 50%), m.p. 200-201° (decomp.). (Found: C, 60.0; H, 4.0; N, 8.4. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 59.7; H, 3.8; N, 8.2%).

7,8-Dimethoxy-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)dione (**XII**): (i) Powdered NaBH_4 (1.54 g.; 0.4 mole) was added to a solution of **VII** (3.72 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml.) and left overnight. It was worked up as described for the preceding

compound. Crystallisation from ethanol yielded XII as colorless needles (1.8 g.; 50%), m.p. 225-226° (decomp.). (Found : C, 61.0; H, 4.4; N, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_4N_2S$ requires C, 60.8; H, 4.2; N, 7.8%).

(ii) XI (0.35 g.; 0.001 mole) suspended in ether (10 ml.) was treated with diazomethane (from 1 g. N-nitrosomethyl urea), left overnight and worked up in the usual way. Crystallisation from ethanol yielded colorless needles (0.35 g.; 90%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 225-226°.

8-*Allyloxy-7-methoxy-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione* (XIII) : Following the procedure described for the preparation of XI, a solution of IX (3.98 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. NaOH (30 ml) was reduced with $NaBH_4$ (1.5 g.; 0.04 mole) and subsequently acidified to afford XIII which, on crystallisation from ethanol gave colorless flakes (2 g.; 50%), m.p. 255-256°. (Found : C, 63.1; H, 4.6; N, 7.5. $C_{20}H_{17}O_4N_2S$ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.4; N, 7.3%).

Chemical Laboratory,
Bihar University,
L. S. College, Muzaffarpur.

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